

Motivational Skills of Teachers and Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in the New Normal

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Abstract. The COVID-19 pandemic profoundly impacted the global education system, necessitating significant adaptations in teaching methods and underscoring the critical role of teacher motivation in student academic performance. This study investigated the correlation between the motivational skills of teachers and the academic performance of Grade 6 students in the new educational environment, often referred to as the "new normal." Focusing on regions such as Oman and the Philippines, where teachers faced challenges like overwork, insufficient salaries, and high student-teacher ratios, this research aimed to identify how teacher motivation influenced student outcomes. Prior research indicated that higher motivational skills among teachers significantly enhanced students' educational outcomes, self-efficacy, and overall academic performance. This study examined these dynamics through a descriptive-correlation non-experimental quantitative research method, employing surveys and statistical analysis to assess the motivational skills of teachers and the academic performance of their students. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between teacher motivation and student academic performance, suggesting that addressing the motivational needs of teachers through adequate support and professional development was crucial. This included implementing diverse motivational strategies to enhance student engagement and academic success, particularly in the context of online learning which became predominant due to the pandemic. This study emphasized the importance of teacher motivation in fostering a productive learning environment and improving student academic performance. The insights gained from this research could inform policies and practices aimed at supporting teachers, thereby enhancing the overall quality of education in the new normal.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher Motivation
2. Academic performance
3. COVID-19 pandemic education adaptation

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1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted various aspects of human life, including socio-economic, psychological, and emotional domains. The education system has also been profoundly affected, necessitating adaptations in teaching methods and highlighting the critical role of teacher motivation in student academic performance. The pandemic-induced shift to online learning has exacerbated existing challenges in teacher motivation, particularly in regions like Oman and the Philippines, where teachers face overwork, insufficient salaries,

and high student-teacher ratios. Teacher motivation plays a pivotal role in students' academic performance. However, the lack of motivation has led many secondary students to lose interest in their academic work, leading to disengagement and a decline in their enthusiasm for learning (Rawahhi et al., 2019). This detachment from their peers can leave students feeling isolated and disinterested. Additionally, their lack of academic support may further contribute to decreased performance.

Prior research indicates that higher motivational skills among teachers significantly enhance students' educational outcomes, self-efficacy, and overall academic performance. Brook et al. (2012) emphasized that motivated teachers employ effective strategies that foster student engagement, self-efficacy, and academic success. Uyulgan and Akkuzu (2014) noted that motivation is a fundamental concept in determining the success and failure of students in the educational system. A motivated teacher will make more efforts in the classroom to positively influence the learner's behavior.

In terms of academic achievement, motivation has been found to influence each student's unique academic performance favorably. Poor academic performance or high failure rates can lead to unacceptable attrition, decreased graduate throughput, and increased educational costs (Malasaga et al., 2018). There is a noticeable lack of motivation among students in Oman on a global scale. Statistics have revealed varying academic success rates among public school students in Sumail, Oman, ranging from 62 percent to 75 percent. These differences are particularly evident among students in grade 11 and grade 12. Moreover, a report from the Ministry of Education indicated that students in the 11th and 12th grades exhibit low academic performance in their classes (Ministry of Education, 2016).

Similarly, the essence of teacher motivation encourages Filipino learners to continue realizing their goals and accomplish their tasks. Fil-

ipino learners are motivated when connected with their classmates and teachers, simply giving the students updates and a positive word to lighten up their day. However, teachers in the Philippines, especially those in the Department of Education, are overworking based on the teaching hours and high student-teacher ratio. Sometimes, because of the numerous reports, lesson plans, and other paperwork that a teacher needs to finish, they cannot give enough time to teach their students (Albert, 2013). Further, salaries for public school teachers are stagnant, and some are underpaid. Their salary is insufficient to pay their bills and other liabilities; others choose to have loans to satisfy their needs (Lopez Irene, 2017).

The devastating impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has intensified the situation. Some students have been victims of stress and depression; thus, teachers' motivation is needed to boost the students' confidence amidst online learning. No study has been conducted in the Division of Digos City, specifically at Pedro V. Basalan Elementary School, to investigate teachers' motivational skills and their impact on students' academic performance during the pandemic. Therefore, it is crucial and timely for the researcher to conduct this study to propose a plan of action for teachers to enhance their motivational skills.

Academic performance is the outcome of education—the extent to which a student, lecturer, or institution has achieved their educational goals. The influence of lecturers' or teachers' teaching effectiveness on students' learning outcomes as measured by students' academic performance has been the subject of several studies (Malasaga et al., 2019). Exams or continuous assessments are commonly used to assess academic performance, although there is no general agreement on how it should be tested or which aspects are most important, such as procedural knowledge like skills or declarative knowledge like facts.

Many studies have been conducted to determine students' academic performance, often using students' General Point Averages (GPAs) as an indicator of academic achievement (Singh et al., 2019). According to The Higher Education Academy (2020), GPAs measure student academic progress during one's degree studies (cumulative) and/or as the final measure of achievement at the end of one's degree (summative). Additionally, a student's performance or academic achievement is essential in producing the best-quality graduates who will become great leaders and human resources for the country's socio-economic development (Term Paper, 2021).

The findings revealed that the shortage of English teachers and other relevant learning materials dramatically affects the student's performance. Teacher's teaching experience also influences students' performance. Older teachers are often more dedicated and devoted to the service due to their length of service and experience (Carmen, 2019). School-related aspects such as books and school facilities can significantly impact students' academic performance. Taylor (2019) proposed that schools in the twenty-first century will need to continue focusing on a dual mission of providing a classroom and school environment that addresses the development needs of all students and providing a hub for additional support services needed to ensure that high-risk students get on track academically toward a baccalaureate degree.

Motivation is an essential element in the learning process and is significant in facilitating student engagement in academic pursuits. It can be defined as a state or condition that provides impetus to behavior, guiding and maintaining its momentum. Sustained operation of action necessitates both exertion and perseverance. Motivation encompasses interconnected beliefs, perceptions, values, information, and actions. Motivation plays a significant role in driving various behaviors, and it is crucial to

comprehend its significance within an educational context (Suhag, 2020). Learning motivation is a crucial antecedent to deep and impactful learning. Conversely, the lack of this learning component significantly inhibits profound and efficacious learning outcomes (Covington, 2020).

Motivation is crucial in facilitating progressive learning. It enables students to cultivate comprehensive and versatile skills rather than merely engage in rote tasks (Beck, 2021). Learning efficacy is enhanced when students are motivated, enabling them to effectively acquire, critically analyze, and proficiently apply information (Dai, 2020). Internal motivation and external motivation are frequently employed as types of motivation in research studies (Palmer, 2020). Intrinsic motivation is contingent upon an individual's internal emotions, innate instincts, and personal desires. Conversely, external motivation is predicated upon the incentives provided by external circumstances, their intended objectives, and the external stimuli they generate. Intrinsic motivation is derived from an internal source within the individual and is driven by the experience of pleasure and satisfaction derived from engaging with challenging tasks.

The present study examined the associations between achievement motivation, attitude, and academic performance among Malaysian university students. Their study found a significant correlation between self-concept and academic achievement among students. Studies also indicated a positive correlation between achievement motivation and academic performance in children (Abu Bakar, 2019). A study examined the relationship between student motivation and academic achievement among undergraduates at UniSZA, revealing a statistically significant and positive correlation between motivation and academic achievement (Alsmadi, 2020). Another study investigated the relationship between university students' academic performance and de-

mographic characteristics, motivation factors, and learning styles, identifying a strong correlation between motivation sources and students' academic performance (Mahyuddin, 2019).

Therefore, teachers' motivational skills, school administrators' support, and parent involvement benefit students by developing their self-motivation, boosting their confidence, and establishing rapport with their classmates. Students are encouraged to perform well in class despite their difficulties because they feel sustained and motivated by their environment.

1.1. Synthesis—The literature review presented above provides an overview of the perspectives and viewpoints of various authors regarding the significance of motivational skills of teachers that can lead to improved student academic performance. The COVID-19 pandemic has notably disrupted various facets of life, significantly affecting socio-economic, psychological, and emotional domains, including the education sector. This disruption has necessitated a shift to new learning methods, particularly online learning, posing a challenge for students and teachers in maintaining motivation. Teacher motivation is crucial for enhancing student academic performance, yet the pandemic has exacerbated the decline in teacher motivation, leading to student disengagement and decreased enthusiasm for learning. The research underscores that motivated teachers employ effective strategies that foster student engagement, self-efficacy, and academic success, highlighting the importance of teacher motivation in educational outcomes (Brook et al., 2012; Uyulgan Akkuzu, 2014). Addressing motivational challenges among teachers and students, particularly in pandemic-affected environments, is essential for improving academic performance and overall educational quality. These statements will guide the researcher in conducting her study, forming conclusions, and making recommendations. The literature review will also serve as a framework for the researcher to follow through

out the research process. It will also serve as a reference for the researcher to support and justify any findings that arise from the statistical analysis and interpretation.

1.2. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—

This study is anchored on the Theory of Needs of Abraham Maslow and the Self-Determination Theory. Some writers say motivation is linked to daily needs and the desire to perform better. Maslow's (1943) need-based theory of motivation proposes that a person has five basic needs: physiological, security, affiliation, esteem, and self-actualization. Pay, food, shelter, clothing, and comfortable working conditions are physiological needs. The security needs include safety, fair treatment, threat protection, and job security. Affiliation needs the desire to be loved, accepted, and a part of a group, whereas esteem needs include the desire for recognition, respect, achievement, autonomy, and independence. Subsequently, the highest level of Maslow's need theory includes self-actualization needs, which must realize one's full potential or self-development; the author refers to this as the pinnacle of one's calling. Once a condition is met, it is no longer a need, according to Maslow. It no longer motivates employee behavior; they are motivated by a need at the next level up the hierarchy. As a result, motivation is directly related to an individual's needs, and as those needs are met, the level of motivation decreases or diminishes over time. Self-determination theory, on the one hand, focuses on the idea of the person's ability to make decisions and manage their own life. This ability is critical to one's mental health and well-being. People who have self-determination believe they have control over their choices and lives. It also affects motivation; people are more motivated to act when they believe their actions have a positive outcome (Cherry, 2021). This theory was developed by Edward Deci and Ryan's framework for studying human personality and motivation. SDT articulates the roles

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study

of intrinsic and types of extrinsic motivation in cognitive and social development and individual differences. Perhaps more importantly, SDT recommendations consider how social and cultural factors influence people’s well-being and performance quality (CSDT, 2021). Thus, these two theories best explain why teachers have low or high motivational skills. Satisfying all teachers’ needs and desires will increase their moti-

vational skills. If this happens, students will be motivated to do their part because their teachers influence and encourage them to do their best. The diagram that follows illustrates the flow of the research. The action initiated is using teachers’ motivational skills, and it hopes to affect the academic performance of Grade 6 students in the new normal. This approach is hoped to increase the student’s academic performance.

1.3. Statement of the Problem—The general purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between the motivational skills

of teachers and the academic performance of Grade 6 students in the new normal. Specifically, this research study aimed to answer the following research objectives.

- (1) What are the motivational skills of teachers in terms of intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation?
- (2) What is the level of academic performance of the grade six learners?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between the motivational skills of teachers and the academic performance of grade six learners?

1.4. Null Hypothesis—In this study, the Null Hypothesis was evaluated using a significance threshold of 0.05. Hypothesis 1: There is no significant correlation between the motivational techniques employed by teachers and the academic achievements of sixth-grade students.

disciplines on how teachers boost their motivational skills, especially in this challenging time, to respond to the various calls of global demands effectively. School Administrators. This study’s findings were beneficial to school heads. The school head can utilize the vital information from this research study to improve teachers’ various skills and competence, which will directly affect students’ academic performance. As instructional leaders, school heads are tasked with implementing different instructions to promote teachers’ pedagogy in realizing the learning institutions’ goals, missions, and visions. Teachers. The findings of this research study are

1.5. Significance of the Study—The following are considered beneficiaries of the study: DepEd Officials. The result of this study served as baseline data for the motivational skills of teachers and how they affect students’ academic performance. Further, this study will serve as the basis for DepEd Officials to initiate various seminars and relevant training across many

helpful to teachers in determining what strategies they will employ to motivate their learners, who are vulnerable to many stresses. Future Researchers. The findings of this study may encourage them to conduct similar studies in other areas. This study is an additional source of reference and inquiries for their investigation relative to the present study.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study’s design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to proofread this work during its preparation meticulously. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized in terms of proofreading to enhance the manuscript’s overall quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI’s growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a descriptive-correlation non-experimental quantitative research method. It was descriptive because the data were presented in quantitative descriptions on “Motivational Skills of Teachers and Academic Performance of Grade Six Teachers. According to Gay (2006), descriptive-correlation design determines and supports how things are. A questionnaire is used when conducting a survey, interview, or observation; the data is usually collected.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study was conducted in Pedro V. Basalan Elementary School Division of Digos City. The respondents of this study were the 12 intermediate teachers of the research locale to answer the first set of questionnaires on the motivational skills of teachers through self-appraisal. A universal sampling procedure was utilized in this study to determine the respondents considering the small number of teacher-respondents in the research locale

Table 1. Number of Learners and Teachers by Grade Level

Grade Level	Number of Learners	Number of Teachers
Grade 6 Smart	40	2
Grade 6 Sapphire	42	1
Grade 6 Silver	40	1
Grade 6 Starlite	40	2
Total	162	6

2.3. Research Instrument—In this study, two (2) sets of questionnaires were used. They were researcher-made questionnaires validated by the study’s experts and later subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach’s alpha. The first set of questionnaires focused on teachers’ motivational skills, while the second set focused on the academic performance of grade six learners.

Fig. 2. Gantt Chart

Table 2. Level of Motivational Skills of the Teacher

Range of Means	Level	Description
4.30 – 5.00	Very High	When the provisions of the motivational skills of teachers is manifested all the time.
3.30 – 4.29	High	When the provisions of the motivational skills of teachers is frequently manifested.
2.30 – 3.29	Fair	When the provisions of the motivational skills of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.30 – 2.29	Low	When the provisions of the motivational skills of teachers is rarely manifested.
0 – 1.29	Very Low	When the provisions of the motivational skills of teachers is never manifested.

To determine the level of academic performance of the grade six learners, the following continuum, based on the DepEd rating system, was used.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The steps involved in this investigation are as follows: A letter seeking permission for this research study was sent to the DepED superintendent of Digos City Division, Melanie Estacio, CESO VI, and the School Principals concerned. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the concerned school division superintendent and principals, the researcher constructed a questionnaire, validated by the experts, and eventually subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach alpha. After permission had been granted for this study to be conducted in Pedro V. Basalan Elementary School, the Division of Digos City, and after the expert validators had

thoroughly examined the research questionnaire, the researchers launched the questionnaire into the field. They retrieved them from the respondents personally after a few days. The data generated from the survey was collated and tallied personally by the researcher. The raw scores were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation, after which the researcher subjected it to analysis and interpretation.

2.5. Data Analysis—The statistical analysis involved the following tools: Average Weighted Mean was utilized to determine the level of teachers’ motivational skills and the academic performance of grade six learners. Pearson’s r was employed to ascertain the signifi-

Table 3. Level of Academic Performance of the Grade Six Learners

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
4.20–5.00	5	Advanced	At this level, the student exceeds the core knowledge, skills, and understanding requirements and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
3.40–4.19	4	Proficient	At this level, the student has developed the fundamental knowledge skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
2.60–3.39	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
1.80–2.59	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge skills and core understanding but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
1.00–1.79	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

cant relationship between learners’ motivational skills and the academic performance of grade six students.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the problems in this study. They are thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Level of the motivational skills of teachers in terms of extrinsic motivation, Level of the motivational skills in terms of intrinsic motivation, and Significant relationship between motivational skills of teachers and academic performance of grade 6 learners in the new normal.

Table 4 shows the level of motivational skills of teachers in terms of extrinsic motivation. In this discussion, the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Fosters a positive learning environment with a rating of 4.45 or very high, Encourages interpersonal relationships among learners in the classroom with a rating of 4.35 or very high, Creates a home within a classroom with a rating of 4.33, Implements classroom responsive policies with a rating of 4.29 or high, and Offers monetary rewards with a rating of 4.10 or high. It got an overall rating of 4.30,

or very high. This also means that the motivational skills of teachers in terms of extrinsic motivation were often manifested. This finding aligns with the research conducted by Springer et al. (2010), which examined the impact of both monetary and non-monetary rewards on teacher motivation. Their study revealed that while monetary incentives provided an immediate boost, non-monetary rewards such as professional development opportunities and public recognition had a more enduring effect on motivation and performance.

Table 4. Level of Motivational Skills of Teachers in Terms of Extrinsic Motivation

	Mean	Description
a. Offers monetary rewards	4.10	High
b. Creates a home within a classroom	4.33	Very High
c. Implements classroom responsive policies	4.29	High
d. Fosters a positive learning environment	4.45	Very High
e. Encourages interpersonal relationships among learners in the classroom	4.35	Very High
Overall	4.30	Very High

This is further supported by Firestone (2014), who emphasized the critical role of extrinsic motivation in enhancing teacher performance and professional development. Firestone highlighted that although financial incentives and recognition can lead to immediate improvements in teacher behavior and student outcomes, it is crucial to balance these with strategies that promote intrinsic motivation. Policymakers and

educational leaders are encouraged to adopt a holistic approach to motivation that incorporates both extrinsic and intrinsic elements to foster a supportive and effective teaching environment.

Table 5 presents the level of motivational skills of teachers in terms of intrinsic motivation. In this discussion, the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Recognizes achievement

of the learners with a rating of 4.34 or very high, helps learners achieve their goal through technical assistance with a rating of 4.31 or very high, Creates an environment that fosters belongingness and security with a rating of 4.30 or very high, challenges everyone to work productively with a rating of 4.29 or higher, and empowers learners to work independently with a rating of 4.20. It obtains an overall mean rating of 4.28 or high. This also means that teachers' motivational skills in terms of extrinsic motivation are often manifested. This finding supports Osterman's (2000) research, which indicates that intrinsically motivated teachers generally experience greater job satisfaction and well-being. The sense of fulfillment derived

from their teaching and their positive impact on students contribute significantly to their sense of purpose and professional identity. This internal satisfaction can be a protective factor against burnout and stress, thus encouraging long-term professional retention. Kusurkar (2013) further supports this notion, highlighting that intrinsically motivated teachers are more committed, creative, and effective in their teaching practices. Intrinsic motivation fosters deeper engagement and persistence, essential for creating a positive learning environment. Teachers with high intrinsic motivation are likelier to innovate their teaching methods and establish meaningful relationships with their students.

Table 5. Level of Motivational Skills of Teachers in Terms of Intrinsic Motivation

	Mean	Description
a. Creates an environment that fosters belongingness and security	4.30	Very High
b. Recognizes achievement of the learners	4.34	Very High
c. Challenges everyone to work productively	4.29	High
d. Empowers learners to work independently	4.20	High
e. Helps learners achieve their goals through technical assistance	4.31	Very High
Overall	4.28	High

Table 6 displays the data on the significant relationship between teachers' motivational skills and the academic performance of grade 6 learners in the new normal. The r-value

obtained is .83, which shows a high correlation between the independent and the dependent variables. It created a p-value of 0.0180, lower than the 0.05 significance level.

Table 6. Significant Relationship Between Motivational Skills of Teachers and Academic Performance of Grade 6 Learners in the New Normal

Variables	r-value	Degree of Correlation	P-value	Decision
Motivational Skills (x)				
Academic Performance (Y)	.83	High	0.0180	Reject Null Hypothesis

Note: Significance when $P < 0.05$

This finding leads to the conclusion that a significant relationship exists between teachers' motivational skills and the academic performance of grade 6 learners in the new normal. This finding implies that the more motivated the learners, the better they perform academically. Several studies have reiterated that higher motivational skills of teachers can envisage the students' educational outcomes and achievement and improve their self-efficacy (Brook et al., 2012). The concept of motivation is one of the essential factors in determining the success and failure of a student. A fundamental concept for teachers and students is distinguishing the root cause of failure and success in the entire education system (Uyulgan Akkuzu, 2014). A motivated teacher will make more efforts in the classroom to pass on adequate information to his students to influence the learner's behavior, most preferably and positively.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter summarized the findings, conclusions, and recommendations the researcher drew after analyzing and interpreting the findings. The study sought to determine the level of teachers' motivational skills and the academic performance of grade 6 learners.

The study employed a non-experimental descriptive survey research design to investigate the research problem. It was descriptive because the data were presented in quantitative descriptions of the "Motivational skills of teachers and academic performance of grade 6 learners in the new normal". According to Good (2005), this research method merely described tasks. It presented the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or events involving analysis, classification, and measurement. It involved varied information regarding the current or present condition (Deauna, 2005).

The study was conducted at all public elementary schools in the Division of Digos City, particularly Pedro V. Basalan Elementary School. The respondents were the six teachers who answered the first set of questionnaires. A universal sampling procedure was used in this study, considering the minimal number of respondents.

4.1. Findings—This study revealed that teachers' motivational skills established a relationship with learners' academic performance. This simply means that the more the teacher motivates the learners, the better the learners perform in the academy.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The teachers' motivational skills in terms of extrinsic motivation are High. The level of motivational skills of teachers in terms of intrinsic motivation is High, and there is a significant relationship between the motivational skills of school heads and the academic performance of grade nine learners.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this

study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that DepEd develop policies on classroom observation where the student's motivation is evident, as observed by the school head. Motivational skills are critical to entice learners to appreciate the teaching-learning situations in the classroom. The school heads should have strengthened their instructional and supervisory activities to intensify their technical assistance to teachers so that learning happens optimally. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study be conducted on the motivational skills of school heads about other variables in the classroom context.

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